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JIS

Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS)

Vision

“ENRICHING BEAUTIFUL MINDS TOWARDS INTELLIGENT MINDS”

The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) aims to disseminate scholarly research articles and papers to the wider community with the aim of offering an academic and scientific platform that provides an outlet to authors. The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) is an open access online journal. Initially, the JIS will provide an online version, but is planning a print version later in this academic journey. The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) focuses on a high-quality academic research articles and papers. All categories of research are of interest to the JIS, including insightful empirical studies, conceptual papers, commentary, essays, and theoretical articles.

JIS is an interdisciplinary platform and invites authors, academics, students, researchers, leaders, managers, scientists for their contributions in the disciplines of sciences, sociology, education, philosophy, humanities and management. Articles and Papers of scientific and academic rigour in Qualitative, Quantitative, Mixed or Blend methods are welcome.

JIS intends to publish two issues per annum (May and November).

Submissions to, and Publication in, the JIS is free.

All papers submitted for publication will be peer reviewed.

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Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS)

mission is to “Guide Beautiful Minds towards Intellectual Enrichment”

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Editorial

Dear Readers,

It is our pleasure to announce our publication of Volume 4, Issue 2 November 2020. It is our aim to bring the multi-interdisciplinary subjects into one platform within which the Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) has successfully published various papers related to different disciplinary areas in our previous four volumes with eight issues. Within these issues, numerous research papers reflecting multi-interdisciplinary subjects have published. In this publication Volume 4, Issue 2, November 2020, we have again attempted to integrate research/scientific papers from various subject areas. This accumulates scientific papers from the areas of psychology, research methodology, political sciences, and economics. The JIS wishes to thank the author(s) and the reviewers for making this issue successful in publication.

The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) receives number of manuscripts submission for publication consideration. For this Volume 4, Issue 2, November 2020, more than twenty manuscripts were submitted by authors from different disciplines. Among these submitted manuscripts only five were accepted after peer review, other submitted manuscripts were rejected during initial screening, editorial reviews and some were rejected during the peer review process. The JIS follows strict guidelines of Publication Ethic and Malpractices (PEMS), in regard to this, one of the manuscripts which was accepted after peer review had to be forcefully removed from publication after the completion of paper layout design, it was due to the journal's PEMS guidelines. It is highly advisable to all author(s) to follow the publication ethic. It is a moral duty of an author(s) to practice publication ethic- submitting the same manuscript to more than one journal while the paper is in the review process is considered as malpractice and is an offence to publication ethics, which can/may also be considered as a Publication Dysfunctional Behavioural Practices (PDBP).

Our next issue will be published in May 2021 for which we invite researchers, managers, leaders, scientists, students and others for paper submission. The call for paper submission is also announced in the journal's announcement portal
<http://journalofinterdisciplinarysciences.com/announcement/>.

The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) is an open access, which offers free submissions, free publication and free open access to download its published research paper from the journal's website <http://journalofinterdisciplinarysciences.com/>.

It is recommended that all author(s) submitting their manuscript to JIS are advised to read the author guidelines from the journal website
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Let us join and collaborate together to **ENRICH the BEAUTIFUL MINDS
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Mani Man Singh Rajbhandari. Ph.D.
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